

Privatization of Higher Education in India

Issues, Challenges and Suggestions for Quality Improvement

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Abstract

Higher education is of paramount importance for economic and social development of both developed and developing countries of the world. Higher education institutions have the greater responsibility for equipping individuals with advanced knowledge and skills required for positions of responsibility in public and private sectors, essential for quality development of society as a whole (Gupta, 2008). Since government has failed to respond quickly to the demand of changing society and aspirations of individuals and learners, there has been a mushroom growth of private institution to meet such needs and aspirations. **This papers aim to explore the factors, challenges and need of privatization of higher education in India by analysing different research studies, books, reports, policies, programmes and practices of teacher education in India. Attempt has also been made in this study to provide valuable suggestions to improve quality in private higher education institutions. The findings of the study will be helpful to the higher education personnel, policy makers to know the need, factors responsible for privatisation of higher education, to make decision, necessary regulatory arrangement for quality improvement in private higher education institutions.**

Key words:- Privatisation, Quality Improvement

1. Introduction

Across the globe, Private higher education is one of the most dynamic and fastest-growing segments of postsecondary education at the turn of the 21st century. A combination of unprecedented demand for access to higher education and the

inability or unwillingness of governments to provide the necessary support has brought private higher education to the forefront (Albatch, 1999). Private higher education is growing worldwide in response to a number of factors and with a variety of goals—meeting the demand for advanced levels of knowledge and technological skills that exceeds the supply; providing more choices or differentiated products to meet the specific demands of the students as consumers and clients; more feasibly implementing variable fee structures on the basis of ability to pay; adopting practices from business management to increase accountability and economic efficiency; shouldering some governmental burdens; rectifying in egalitarian, over-, or misuse of public provision of higher education; making the government focus on its prime duty towards literacy and basic education; saving public subsidies for public goods; generating revenues and making innovations through experimentation—there can be significant variations at the socio-cultural and national levels (Gupta, 2008, James, 1993; World Bank, 1999; Rose, 2002).

The private sector can also be given credit for the expansion of higher education in most countries in the last three decades. It can provide quality education to the elite, vocational education to the needy, and low quality education to those who neither merit nor can afford a better education. It can also provide education to those who are already employed, through distance or online education on an “anytime, anywhere” basis (Gupta, 2008).

2. CURRENT SCENARIO OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

India has the credit of running the third largest higher education system in the world, next to United States and China to educate all the to youth in the age group having 18 to 23 having a total of **993 universities**, 39931 **Colleges** (affiliated and constituent Institutions of Central and State Public Universities) and 10725 Stand Alone **Institutions**, enrollment of more than 3.73 corer students with 14.16 lacs teachers in various level of higher education in different field of study across the country. Total enrolment in higher education has been estimated to be 37.4 million with 19.2 million male and 18.2 million female. Female constitute 48.6% of the total enrolment. Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher education in India is 26.3%,

which is calculated for 18-23 years of age group. GER for male population is 26.3% and for females, it is 26.4%. For Scheduled Castes, it is 23% and for Scheduled Tribes, it is 17.2% as compared to the national GER of 26.3%. [All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE Report, 2018-19)].

Table-1 Number and type of Universities in India.

Type of university	Number of Universities
Central University	46
Central Open University	1
Institution of National Importance	127
State Public University	371
Institution Under State Legislature Act	5
State Open University	14
State Private University	304
State Private Open University	1
Deemed University- Government	34
Deemed University- Government Aided	10
Deemed University- Private	80
Grand Total	993

Figure-1 Growth of Universities and Colleges in India

Source:- (AISHE-2019)

3. Factor responsible for Privatization of Higher Education in India

Privatization is defined as a process whereby private individuals or organizations own and control educational institution. It is a process of management of institutions by private body or organization. In the context of higher education, it refers to the management of colleges by private body or organization registered under certificate of registration of society – XXI – Act 1860. Private body or organization has got both administrative and financial autonomy to run educational institution with minimal control of the government and universities.

The following factors are responsible for emergence of private sectors in higher education in India.

1. Due to Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act' or '*Right to Education Act* which provide free and compulsory education for children between the age of 6 and 14 in India under Article 21A of the Indian Constitution, literacy level continuously increasing at primary and secondary schools which required a large number of higher education institutions.
2. India is a poor country where a large number of people are living below the poverty line. These are deprived of even basic amenities like food, water, health and housing facilities on which the survival of human being depends. It is because of this reason that the state has kept education at number six on its priority list. Under these circumstances, the states have no other alternative except reducing the percentage of their planned expenditure on education, particularly on higher education (Ahmad & Siddiqui, 2003).
3. Government has trickled down its expenditure on higher education. In the tenth five year plan document, it was stated that, —Since budget resources are limited and such resources as are available, need to be allocated to expand primary education, it is important to recognize that universities

must make greater efforts to supplement resources from the government. University fees are very low and in many universities have not been raised in decades. A substantial hike in university fees is essential. (Gautam, Parihar & Khare, 2015).

4. Massification of higher education leading to a phenomenal growth of institutions of higher learning and student registration which the state cannot manage with its limited human and material resources.
5. There is no political intervention of either centre or state govt ruling party in private institution for that they have autonomy and freedom to run their academic and administrative affairs.
6. In general, private universities and colleges offer better facilities and equipment and a better teacher-pupil ratio than state (public) universities.
7. Private Universities and Colleges always look for up gradation of the technologies that what they use in their institutes so that they are always up to date to the present times.
8. Privatisation can respond to market demand for labour in a more efficient and prompt manner than the public sector, which finds it very difficult to introduce flexibility in its operations of HRD (Reddy & Tenniti, 2003).

4. THE CHALLENGES AHEAD

Though higher education plays numerous roles, in the rapid changing global and local landscape, the higher education institutions worldwide are facing formidable challenges and constraints as unprecedented demand for access to higher education and inability or unwillingness of the governments to provide the same, inadequate funding, demands for accountability, weak infrastructure and institutional management, lack of efficient administrative body, weak and inexperienced faculty, overcrowded classrooms, low levels of teacher training programmes, irrelevant curriculum, student unrest, spineless administration, dubious examination etc. (Gupta, 2008 ; Bharathi, 2013).

The biggest challenges for the higher education in the 21st century is to strike a balance between the market pressures in terms of economy, efficiency and competition, on the one hand, and preservation of traditional values, autonomy, their

role as, social critique and political vanguard, on the other (Gupta, 2008). Higher education in India continues to be in a deepening financial crisis, with escalating cost and increasing needs of the system, on the one hand, and declining resources, on the other, despite large investments made on higher education. Hence, of late, several policy proposals have been made including privatization (Singh, 2003)

5. Suggestion for quality improvement in private higher education institution.

The following suggestions are highly essential for quality improvement in private higher education institution.

- a) A separate regulatory body in association with UGC, NAAC, NBA, NIEPA should be constituted at central and regional levels to monitor the private universities.
- b) The Government must have a monitoring body to look over the funding affair of private university and colleges so that it must not be misused.
- c) All Private institutions should encourage for voluntary undergo for institution's evaluation process of self-assessment and external assessment through various accredited bodies like NAAC, NBA.
- d) Admission to such colleges may be determined by common entrance tests and terminal degrees may not be awarded before passing a national test of competency.
- e) Selected college in Private sector may be given academic, financial and administrative autonomy on the basis of their past achievement and assessment by accreditation body like NAAC.
- f) Bright students of weaker sections should be given cost free education.
- g) The private institutions should not enhance the fee structure without the approval of the government.
- h) In private university some government official should act as board of members in administration.
- i) There must not be any hidden cost in private institutions.
- j) Attempt should be made by the private universities and colleges to contact alumni and seek their valuable support in strengthening the financial resources of the universities.

- k) Effort should be made to reap the benefit of research by institute-industry collaboration. The research should be productive in nature. Spending on research should be attached to the utility of project.
- l) Study loan must be provided to students at low rate of interest to meet the cost of their education.
- m) There must not be any impartiality in awarding marks to students.

6. Conclusion

This paper explored the reason and factors responsible for privatisation of higher education in India. The government of India is lack for a clear cut policy regarding privatisation of higher education. Various bills introduced in the Parliament regarding private higher education, stuck at various levels. There is a urgent need of a clear cut policy for the establishment and maintenance of private higher education institution. Regulatory arrangement must be put in place before the private sector is allowed to enter the educational sector. However an improvement in the standards of higher education could be achieved only through a balanced relationship between the Public and the Private Sectors.

References:-

1. Ahmad, N. & Siddiqui, M. A. (2008). Private Initiatives in Higher Education and Common Entrance Test: Minority Perspective (pp. 180 - 194). In Gupta, A., Levy, D. C., & Powar, K. B. (Eds.).
2. Altbach, P.G.(1999). **Private Prometheus: Private higher education and development in the 21st century**. Westport: Greenwood Press.
3. Bharati P. (2013). Education privatization: causes, consequences and planning implications. Paris. UNESCO.
4. Chougale, S. (2014). Privatization of higher education in india: college teachers perception. *National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research In Arts & Education*. Volume III, Issue No. 2, 15-25

5. Eisemon, T. O. (1992). *Private initiative and traditions of state control in higher education in sub-Saharan Africa*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
6. Gupta, A. (2008). *Education in the 21st Century: Looking Beyond University*. New Delhi, Shipra Publications.
7. Gautam, R., Parihar, A.S., & S. Khare(2015). Analysis of globalization/privatization of higher education in India. International Conference on Science, Technology and Management. University of Delhi. Retrived from <http://data.conferenceworld.in/ICSTM2/P2542-2549.pdf>.
8. James, E., & Benjamin, G. (1998). *Public policy and private education in Japan*. London: Macmillan.
9. Ko-Ho Mok. (2005). Globalisation and Governance: Educational Policy Instruments and Regulatory Arrangements. *International Review of Education*. 51(4), 289–311.
10. MHRD (2019). **Annual Report: All India Survey on Higher Education** New Delhi ,Government of India.
11. Ravi, S. S. (2011). *A comprehensive study of Education*, New Delhi: prentice Hall of India.
12. Reddy,R., Manvhala,C. & Amareswaran, N.(2015). Privatisation of professional education. *University News*, A.I.U, New Delhi.
13. Rose, F. (2002). *Privatization in Education: Trends and Consequences*, Education, Research and Foresight, UNESCO. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0024/002464/246485E.pdf>
14. Singh, L.C. (2003). *Privatisation of Higher Education*. *University News*, A.I.U, New Delhi.
15. Sharma, V. (2009). *Crisis of Higher Education in India*, retrieved from <http://indiaeducrisis.wordpress.com/>
16. Srivastava, K. (2012). Private Sector makes a mark in higher education, Dnaindia, Retrieved, from http://www.dnaindia.com/academy/report_private-sector-makes-a-markin-higher-education_1617045
17. Sharma, G.D., (1998). Contribution of Higher Education in National Development, *Journal of Higher Education*, Vol. 21, No. 2, pp. 201-223.

18. Shankar, A. (2016). Role of Private sector in higher education. Retrieved from http://www.prsindia.org/administrator/uploads/general/1453203086_Role%20of%20Private%20Sector%20in%20Higher%20Education.pdf
19. World Bank. 1994. *Higher education : the lessons of experience (English)*. Development in practice. Washington DC ; retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/303461468328502540/Higher-education-the-lessons-of-experience>.
20. Walia, H.S.(2012). Cost of privatization, Tribune India, Retrieved,from <http://www.tribuneindia.com /2011/20110614 /edu.htm#1>.
21. United Nations (1998). UN declaration on higher education for the 21st century: Vision and action. World Conference on Higher Education. volume IV:Preparing for a sustainable future, higher education and sustainable human development: Paris:UN.
22. UNESCO (1996). Learning: The Treasure Within. Report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education in 21st century. Paris: UNESCO.